

THERMAL SHOCK RESISTANCE OF HYBRID PARTICULATE-FILLED EPOXY COMPOSITES

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SUMMARY: For improvement in toughness of epoxy casting materials, hybrid particle-filled composites have been reported. Since toughening mechanisms of hard and soft particles are effective at the same time, large improvement can be expected. In this study, an effect of hybrid filler on thermal shock resistance using silica particulate as hard filler and MBS rubber as soft filler is examined. The thermal shock test which we have been proposed was conducted on mono-filler and hybrid-filler composites. The results were concluded that, hard and soft hybrid filler effect on thermal shock was smaller than that on fracture toughness. This tendency is due to the debonding of silica filler and matrix interface.

KEYWORDS: thermal shock, epoxy resin, hybrid filler, fracture toughness, particulate-filled resin, thermal shock test, silica filler, MBS rubber.

INTRODUCTION

The epoxy resin has many good properties as insulating materials, such as high insulation resistance, adhesive property, moldability, *etc.*. Unfortunately, the epoxy casting materials usually show low cracking resistance. Therefore, the second phase materials are added to the resin for improvement in toughness. The second phase materials often consist of either a hard inorganic filler [1] or a soft rubbery material [2]. The hard particulate branches off the crack propagation and makes it zigzag way, that is crack pinning effect which improves fracture toughness. On the other hand, soft particulate locally deforms matrix resin and by this energy consumption the fracture toughness also increases. Since these toughening mechanisms are effective at the same time, recently new composites *i.e.*, hybrid particulate-filled epoxy resins have been reported as highly toughened insulating materials [3, 4]. For these composites, in which both hard and soft particles are filled, large improvement in toughness can be expected.

In application of these epoxy resins or epoxy based composites in electric and electronic fields, high resistance to thermal shock is required to guarantee the high reliability. Failure by thermal shock is a complex phenomena because it is greatly affected by many factors, such as the geometry of the testing sample, the thermal and mechanical properties, and so forth.

We had already proposed a new test method to evaluate the thermal shock resistance of the epoxy resins and particulate filled resins [5~8]. The thermal shock test is easily conducted in laboratory, and the thermal shock resistance is evaluated analytically based on linear fracture mechanics. In our previous studies, the thermal shock resistance of hard particulate filled resin and soft second phase filled resin are reported. Both types of toughened resins showed improvement in thermal shock resistance.

In this study, effect of hybrid filler on thermal shock resistance using silica particulate as a hard filler and MBS rubber particulate as a soft filler was examined.

EXPERIMENTAL

Materials

The thermal shock test was conducted for neat resin, silica filled composite, rubber filled composite and silica & rubber hybrid type composite. The neat resin or the matrix resin of the other composites was bisphenol-type epoxy (epoxy equivalent weight = 5.1 - 5.6 equiv./kg) cured with acid anhydride hardener. The silica filler was angular-shaped particulate without surface treatment and the average diameter of the filler was about 13 μm . The Metacryl-Butadiene-Styrene (MBS) rubber was used as rubber filler material. This filler consisted of under micron particle, which made about 100 μm size cluster.

Two series of mono-filler composites and two series of hybrid-filler composites were used. The silica filler content was varied from neat resin to 300 phr (per hundred resin), and the MBS filler content was varied from neat resin to 15 phr respectively. Hybrid filler composites content of hard filler and soft filler were also changed as shown in Table 1. The MBS content was fixed 10 phr for one of the hybrid composites series, and the silica content was fixed 200 phr for the other series.

Table 1 Composition of tested materials.

	silica filler (phr)	MBS rubber filler (phr)
hard particulate filled composites	100, 200, 300	0
soft particulate filled composites	0	5, 10, 15
hybrid particulate filled composites	100, 200, 250, 300, 320 200	10 5, 10, 15

Thermal Shock Test Method

In this test, pre-notched disk shaped specimen was checked whether crack was propagated or not from the tip of notch after thermal shock. The test specimen of 60 mm diameter and 10 mm thickness disk has a radial direction pre-notch as shown in Fig.1. The notch length (c in Fig.1) was kept 6 mm. The specimen held between two heat insulators was put into the cooling bath which consisted of dry ice / pentane coolant system. Then, since the disk was cooled from the cylindrical surface to the center along the radius, thermal stress for mode-I fracture was created at the tip of the pre-notch. The temperature difference was controlled by changing the initial temperature of the specimen. The thermal shock resistance was evaluated quantitatively as the minimum temperature difference at which initial notch propagated.

Fig. 1 The size and shape of thermal shock test specimen [5,7].

Morphological Study

Fracture toughness was measured by 3 point bending with single edge notched specimen. The fracture surfaces near crack starting portion after the thermal shock test and the fracture toughness test were compared. The surface was observed by SEM equipped with back scattering image (BEI) detector, which could easily distinguish inorganic filler from matrix resin.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Mono-filler Composites

The silica filled composite and rubber filled composite increased fracture toughness and thermal shock resistance in comparison with neat resin. Fig.2 shows thermal shock test result on (a) silica and (b) MBS filled resin. The open circle denotes that crack initiated and propagated and the solid circle shows that crack did not propagate. The critical temperature difference which corresponds to the minimum temperature difference to initiate the crack from the notch clearly increases with silica filler content, as shown in Fig.2 (a). In the case of the MBS filled resin, thermal shock resistance also improves well. In this figure, solid triangle means that the crack propagation did not occurred but the notch deformed obviously. These tendencies are agree with the other epoxy composites toughened with silica filler [6,8] or CTBN [5].

Fig.2 Effect of filler content on thermal shock resistance.

Hybrid-filler Composites

The hybrid type composite also showed large improvement in fracture toughness [3], but showed constant or slightly decreasing tendency of thermal shock resistance at highly filler content as shown in Fig.3 and Fig.4.

Fig.3 shows the experimental results of the fracture toughness and the thermal shock resistance of hybrid filler composite, in which rubber content was 10 phr constant and silica filler content was varied. The fracture toughness increase linearly. On the other hand, the thermal shock resistance gradually decreases with silica filler content.

Fig.3 Effect of silica filler content on fracture toughness and thermal shock resistance of hybrid composite (rubber ; 10 phr).

The test result of hybrid filler composite in which silica filler content was kept at 200 phr and rubber content was varied is also shown in Fig.4. Same as Fig.3, the fracture toughness increases linearly. On the other hand, in the contrast with the effect of silica filler on the thermal shock resistance shown in Fig.3, the rubber content effect is positive. However, at high rubber content the effect is very small, so that a tendency that the thermal shock resistance of the mono MBS filler composite surpass the hybrid MBS / silica composite over 0.06 volume fraction (*cf.* Fig.2) is recognized.

Fig.4 Effect of rubber filler content on fracture toughness and thermal shock resistance of hybrid composite (silica ; 200 phr).

Thermal Shock Resistance Evaluation Based on Fracture Mechanics and Fractography

To discuss the effect of filler content on thermal shock resistance, thermal stress intensity factor was evaluated with some thermal and mechanical properties. Based on our previous study, the thermal shock resistance ΔT_c is expressed as;

$$\Delta T_c = \frac{(1-\nu) \cdot K_{Ic}}{\alpha \cdot E} \cdot \frac{C_1}{\sqrt{R}} + \frac{k \cdot (1-\nu) \cdot K_{Ic}}{\alpha \cdot E} \cdot \frac{C_2}{h \cdot \sqrt{R^3}}$$

where α is coefficient of thermal expansion, E is elastic modulus, K_{Ic} is fracture toughness, ν is Poisson's ratio, k is thermal conductivity, h is heat transfer coefficient, R is the radius of the disk specimen and C_1 , C_2 are constants determined by the condition of thermal shock test, respectively. The coefficients of thermal shock resistance *i.e.*, the fraction $(1-\nu)K_{Ic}/\alpha E$ in the first term and the fraction $k(1-\nu)K_{Ic}/\alpha E$ in the second term are measured experimentally and they are shown in Fig.5. Because h and R are constant, the evaluated values showed the tendency of increasing thermal shock resistance. These tendencies differed from that of Fig.3. Then, some factors should be considered to evaluate the thermal shock resistance of hybrid filler composites.

Fig.5 Silica filled effect on coefficients of thermal shock resistance.

This difference between experimental and theoretical evaluation was also obtained in the alumina filled resin, because of the poor adhesion, as we had already shown in previous study [7,8]. Then, the fracture surface after thermal shock test and fracture toughness test are observed by SEM and compared each other. Generally silica filler has good adhesion with epoxy matrix resin. For mono filler composite, both fracture surfaces showed good interface bond between silica particle and matrix, but for hybrid filler composite, especially at high silica content, the thermal shock test sample showed debonding at the interface. SEM photographs of fracture surfaces of silica 250 phr and MBS 10 phr hybrid system are shown in Fig.6, where (a) is that after fracture toughness test and (b) is thermal shock test. Obviously Fig.6 (a) shows flat silica fractured surface, that means crack propagate with breaking silica particles. On the other hand, Fig.6 (b) shows filler original surface is recognized between some particles and the matrix.

(a) Fracture toughness test

(b) Thermal shock test

Fig.6 SEM photographs of fracture surfaces of hybrid composite (silica 250 phr & MBS 10 phr).

Then the difference of fracture mechanisms in fracture toughness test and thermal shock test is expected. This weakened interface caused low thermal shock resistance of hybrid filler composites.

CONCLUSION

In this study, thermal shock resistance of hybrid particulate filled composites were examined. The fracture toughness and the thermal shock resistance evaluated is summarized in Fig.7. As shown in Fig.7, hard and soft hybrid filler effect on thermal shock is smaller than that on fracture toughness. This tendency is due to the debonding of silica filler / matrix interface. For this reason, hybrid filler composite should be taken care not to crack if the material used under thermal shock condition.

*Fig.7 Silica & MBS hybrid filler effect on
(a) thermal shock resistance and (b) fracture toughness.*

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